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Abstract. This article gives an information about the linguistic features of toponyms, translation problems of toponyms and translational analysis of toponyms in “Baburname”. The author tried to disclose the geographical names’ meaning in translation and taking an approach to the translation identified the translation methods in this article.

Key words: translation, transliteration, toponymy, toponyms, translational analysis.

Toponymy is the branch of onomastic field concerned with the study of places’ names, that have been considered by most scholars to be a discipline of convergence (or of “synthesis”), i.e. and a discipline concerned with a multiplicity and variety of knowledge in this field which can, therefore, be approached from many different perspectives. In practice, toponymy can be said to involve a considerable number of fields that do not stand in juxtaposition to one another but which are rather very closely interrelated.

Toponymy is the study of the language evolution (etymology) of places’ names as well as the motivation for naming them (historical and geographical aspects). On the other hand, most toponymy focus ed on the etymological study of habitation names, they often overlook feature names and the motivation for naming a location. Most homonymic studies have concentrated on the specific aspect of the place name. The adjective form of the specific is the dominant place-name in English. Prepositional place-names used in a descriptive sense are more rare in English.

The first attempt in article is to interpret and classify toponyms made by ancient Egyptian, Greek, Chinese, Indian, Persian, Byzantine, and Roman historians and geographers as well as in other written sources possible. In the ancient world, along with the creation of historical and geographical works, there was a tradition of interpreting geographical names. However, this etymology of toponyms interpreted differently in this period. Most of the time the origin of place names with some mythical plots tied up. However, geographical names are sometimes misinterpreted often in which the real features of the object, its geographical location, and other features are taken into account.

If we look at the etymology of Uzbek toponyms that some of the works are devoted to the study of microtoponyms of districts or cities because the narrower scope of the toponymic object, the more valid the scientific conclusions. From this point of view, scientific researches as T.Rakhmatov, J.Latipov, H.Kholmuminov, O.Aripov, A.Aslanov, S.Buriev are noteworthy. A.Turobov seriously studied the linguistic analysis of ethnonyms and ethnographical places' name on the example of materials of Samarkand region. O.Begimov defended his dissertation on the linguistic study of the assimilation layer in toponyms.

And also there are several strategies of translating toponyms. The following translation methods should be used during translation of toponyms:

1. Transliteration, transliteration of toponyms in English letters;
2. Word by word translation;
3. Descriptive translation, revealing the content of the meaning expressed by toponyms;
4. Translations were also translated by giving translations of toponyms through comments.

Geographical name can also completely change the appearance of a common noun over a long period of time. For example, Zoroastrians are called "*Mughals*" by Muslims. In Uzbekistan, toponyms such as '*Mughan, Mugkhona*' are left to these firefighters. Names like '*Miq, Miqtepa*' are a vivid reflection of the word 'mug'. Or

khanaqah Khanqa, Dizak (diz, "fortress" in Sogdian) Jizzakh, aqba (Arabic pass) in the form of a hunt, and so on.

Toponyms in "Baburname" appear in the first pages of the work. The toponyms are structured according to the location of the geographical regions that Babur conquered, studied, and lived. Another feature of the place descriptions is that the author not only emphasizes the geographical, geological, and natural advantages of the region, but also it includes the history of the place, the country, mountains, pastures, fortresses, and the fate of famous people. Such a perfect image is one of the factors that make the work interesting and well-structured, in addition to this it gives additional information to the reader of "Baburname".

During translating the toponyms, we sometimes see that they are based on the nature, origin, and certain historical events of the place and the translator reconstructs the toponyms one by one following their originality. Sometimes with comments, sometimes in transliteration. For instance, the word «Итмак довони» transliterated as «Амак Дабан» (Амак Дабан). In the origin version of the text: «сахроси ва шаҳри ва боми ва томи» translates as «the plains, the town of Kesh, the walls and terraces of the houses» (текисликлар, Кеш шаҳри, уйларнинг пешайвони ва деворлари). Instead of the word «Саҳроси» there used «plains» (текисликлар), and instead of «тоғ» used «hill» (баландлик). However, the words mountain and altitude differ sharply in meaning. The main aim of the translator is to translate toponyms according to the geographical concepts, specific to these people, toponymic terms, in general, the origin of the culture and history of the nation. Meanwhile, the translator used the transliteration method to reconstruct the names of Shahrīsabz, the city, and the pass. We can see transliterates in toponyms of "Baburname" such as, "Кеш" as "Kesh", "Самарқанд" as "Samarkand", "Шаҳрисабз" as "Shahr-isabz" and gives definition (Green City) with the help of parenthesis. At this point, translator takes into account national characteristics, linguocultural aspects. As a result, it is offered clarity and an alternative translation option.

To conclude, we often encounter the method of transliteration in the translations of toponyms in the work, but the linguoculturological features of the translations also have a unique image.

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